

Question/Prompts

This prompt will be used to guide focus group discussion. The prompt is around current technology usage in agriculture, agriculture information dissemination, potential benefits and challenges of using technology in agriculture

Refreshers

- [Everyday practice] When and how do farmers usually receive or look for agriculture information? Is it while chatting at the stall, during farmer group meetings, or via WhatsApp messages (or other social media)?
 - Are there any regular village activities that could be used to share agriculture information? (Like community gatherings, farmer meetings, markets, prayer groups, or social events)
 - What do farmers usually use to share information with others? Do they talk directly, send photos or voice messages on WhatsApp, or share videos?
 - What could help make a farming app part of farmers' daily routines? Should it be something simple to use during breaks? Should it be introduced during community events?
 - What would be a good way to combine information from different sources so it's easy to understand and trusted by farmers?

Information dissemination (information ecologies)

- [Actors] Who do farmers usually go to when they need agricultural information?
 - Is it the extension officer, fellow farmers, village leaders, or WhatsApp group (or other social media)?
 - Which people or organisations do you trust most? Why?
 - Eg. Have you ever worked with extension officers or NGOs? What was good or bad about it?
 - Who in your family or community helps you understand new farming information?
- [Technology and infrastructure]. What media or tools are currently used to share agriculture information with farmers? (For example, farmer group meetings, printed posters, village notice boards, radio, Facebook, or WhatsApp?)
 - Which ones are easiest for you? Which ones are hardest?
 - Are there any tools or technologies that are especially useful for spreading agriculture information? Eg. market price boards, community radio, short videos, or voice messages?
 - If a new tool was offered to you, what would make you want to try it?

- [Norms and Values]. Are there things in your community that make it easier or harder to trust new farming advice?
 - What do other farmers here think about trying new farming practices?
 - Is there any traditional knowledge that you still use instead of new advice?
 - How do extension officers (and/or other relevant stakeholders), farmers, and digital platforms currently interact?
 - Do extension officers use social media or WhatsApp to reach farmers? Do farmers prefer face-to-face talks or messages?
- [Rules and Regulations]. Have you heard about any government rules or programs that affect farming?
 - What about subsidies, extension programs, or co-op membership?
 - How do these rules or programs help you get information — or make it harder?

Information sharing practice (social practice theory)

- [Meaning] When you hear new farming advice, how do you decide if it is good or not? What makes advice feel trustworthy to you? Are there some types of information that just do not feel right to you? Why?
- [Materials, tools and resources]. What tools do you use every day to apply farming knowledge? Do you feel these tools are good enough? What would you improve? If you could have any new tools, what would you choose?
- [Skills] What farming skills do you feel most confident about? (for example, planting, pest control, irrigation) What skills or knowledge do you wish you could improve or learn more about? When you want to learn a new farming skill, who usually helps you or teaches you? (for example, family members, neighbours, extension workers)
- **[Linking information ecology with social practice]** Can you tell me about a time when you tried new information in your farm? Where did you get the information? What made you trust or doubt it? How did you put it into practice?
 - Have there been times you decided *not* to use information? What stopped you?
 - What would make it easier for you to keep trying new information?
 - What makes a new tool or practice become part of everyday life for farmers? Is it because it's useful? Because others also use it? Or because someone guides them?